

Overcoming the aberration-limit of a non-corrected Transmission Electron Microscope with computational ghost imaging

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Background incl. aims

The invention of aberration correctors at the end of the 20th century has made modern Transmission Electron Microscopes (TEMs) one of the most sought-after scientific instruments in modern material science and life science laboratories since they now allow to image and characterize samples with the highest lateral (spatial) resolution. [1,2] The most important technological advancement which further increased the interest in TEMs was the invention of spherical aberration correctors. [3,4] Unfortunately, aberration correctors are quite costly and are reaching performance limitations: this has prompted some research groups to work on computational imaging methods to increase the lateral resolution in TEMs.

Here we present the results from a simulated computational ghost imaging (CGI) scheme for TEMs where we demonstrate numerically that it's possible to overcome the resolution limit imposed by aberrations using well-characterized structured probes and a bucket detector.

Methods

In computational ghost imaging the image of the sample (and its spatial information) is computationally recovered by illuminating the sample with a series of known structured beams and collecting the integrated transmitted intensity via a single-pixel bucket detector positioned after the sample. In fact, if the measurement is linear we can see that it can be described in matrix notation with the equation $I = P^T T$ where I is the array containing the N signals recorded by the single pixel detector, P is the array containing the intensity pattern of the N probes and T is the sample transfer function. By knowing both P and I it is possible to recover T and many algorithms exist to this end [5]. We have developed a custom python-based algorithm that allows us to simulate the generation of structured patterns, provides us with the value of the signal measured by a virtual bucket detector (even in presence of noise and realistic coherence effects) and recovers T with three different

reconstruction algorithms: the traditional one, the alternated projection algorithm and the conjugate gradient descent algorithm.

Results

For the generation of the simulated structured patterns we assumed a 300kV microscope with $C_s=2.7\text{mm}$, a 15.4 mrad probe convergence angle and as defocus four times the Scherzer STEM defocus. All other aberrations were neglected since we had such a large value of C_s . The electron modulator is assumed to be in the last condenser aperture, while the sample of choice (a twisted bilayer of MoS₂ – Figure1a) is conventionally positioned in the sample plane. As single pixel detector we used the annular dark field detector, but in principle we could use other single pixel detectors such the bright field detector or those used for energy dispersive X-Ray imaging, electron energy loss spectroscopy or cathodoluminescence.

As it is possible to appreciate from figure 1, our CGI scheme is able to overcome the aberration limit imposed by the instrument (figure 1e) with a two-fold increase in spatial resolution compared to an aberration-limited STEM image (figure 1c) as confirmed by the analysis of their FFTs (figure 1f and d, respectively).

Conclusion

Here we have demonstrated that, if the optical system is well characterized and the aberrations that act on the illumination are known and quantified, it is possible via a computational imaging technique to overcome the aberration-limit.

We are already working on an experimental implementation where the phase plate for structuring the beam has been realized using MEMS technology. As a next step for further improvements, we are working on the possibility to use machine learning (ML) to further optimize our electron modulator and the pattern that it can generate, with should enhance both our simulated results and more importantly the future experimental ones. Moreover, we are also working on a mixed scheme where we also control the scan coil of the TEM to optimize the illumination, increases reliability and acquisition speed, and should allow for the reconstruction of the probe.

Figure 1 Caption: a) schematic of the electron-optical setup, (b,d,f) comparison between the sample atomic potential, the aberration-limited STEM image, and CGI reconstruction and their corresponding FFT (c,e,g). For the CGI reconstruction reported here no noise and no realistic coherence effects (temporal or spatia) were considered, but we have also performed simulations in those scenarios. In the FFT images the yellow inner circle corresponds to 2α , while the red outer circle corresponds 4α , where $\alpha=7.3$ mrad. Scalebar in b,d and f is 0.5nm. In h) is shown an example of a structured

pattern utilized for the CGI reconstruction and in i) is shown complex image of its FFT.

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Graphic:

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Reference:

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